

Supplemental Table 10. Data charting for all studies assessing the association between immigration and GWG.

Author	Year	Country	Study design	Source of GWG data;		Sample size	Significant findings	Non-significant findings	Immigration categories	Study sample primarily included individuals with a vulnerability factor?	Findings
				guideline used	Study population						
Chasan-Taber, L.	2014	USA	Prospective	Medical record; IOM 2009	Hispanic women (Puerto Rican or Dominican Republic heritage) seeking prenatal care at a public clinic from 2006-11	1 276	Significant difference in GWG adequacy (insufficient, adequate, or excessive) according to immigration status (categories: woman born in Puerto Rico/Dominican Republic, parent born in PR/DR, or grandparent born in PR/DR)		Born in Puerto Rico/Dominican Republic (PR/DR); parent born in PR/DR; grandparent born in PR/DR	Yes	S
Chasan-Taber, L.	2016	USA	Prospective	Medical record; IOM 2009	Hispanic women (Puerto Rican or Dominican Republic heritage) seeking prenatal care at a public clinic from 2006-11	1 293	Significant difference in GWG adequacy (insufficient, adequate, or excessive) according to immigration status (born in continental US vs Puerto Rico/Dominican Republic)		Born in Puerto Rico/Dominican Republic (yes/no)	Yes	S
Chasan-Taber, L.	2008	USA	Prospective	Medical records; IOM 1990	Hispanic (primarily Puerto Rican), low-income women receiving prenatal care at a public clinic from 2000-03	770	Lower risk of excessive GWG if <10 years of residence in USA (compared to third generation women)	NS effect of living 10+ years in USA or being a second generation immigrant (as compared to third generation) on excessive or insufficient GWG; NS effect of living <10 years in USA (as compared to being third generation immigrant) on insufficient GWG	Generations in US: <10 yrs residence; ≥10 yrs residence; 2nd generation; 3rd generation	Yes	S & NS
Cheng, H. R.	2015	USA	Retrospective	Birth certificate; IOM 2009	White non-Hispanic and Asian non-Hispanic (Asian Indian, Chinese, Filipino, Japanese, Korean, or Vietnamese) women who were documented in the 2009 Texas birth certificate data	114 632	Among foreign-born Asian women: higher risk of insufficient GWG and lower risk of excessive GWG		US born (yes/no)	No	S
Gutierrez, Y. M.	1999	USA	Prospective	Medical records; IOM 1990	Multi-site study with Hispanic (Mexican American), primiparous adolescents (13-18 years) in San Francisco and San Jose	46	Significant differences in GWG according to length of time living in the USA (3-12 mo, 12-48 mo vs 48-216 mo; time living in USA used as a proxy measure for acculturation)		Length of residence in US: 3-12 mo; 12-48 mo; 84-216 mo	Yes	S
Headen, I.	2018	USA	Prospective	Self-reported ; IOM 2009	Participants of the 1979 National Longitudinal Survey of Youth who were 14-21 years old in 1979	3 300		NS difference in GWG adequacy according to immigration status	Foreign born (yes/no)	No	NS
Huynh, M. H.	2015	USA	Cross-sectional	Birth certificate; IOM 2009	Hispanic, Black non-Hispanic, or White non-Hispanic nulliparous adolescents (age 12-19) who gave birth in New York City from 2008-10	15 715	Non-immigrants have highest prevalence ratio of excessive GWG, and prevalence is lower as time lived in the US decreases (as compared to women who immigrated <5 years ago; results seen in all groups: race, insurance status and age [with the exception of age 12-15])	NS difference in prevalence of excessive GWG in youngest age group (12-15 years) according to immigration status	US-born; foreign born ≥10 yrs ago; foreign born 5-<10 yrs ago; foreign born <5 yrs ago	Yes	S & NS

Kowal, C.	2012	Canada	Retrospective	Self-reported; Health Canada 2010 (IOM 2009)	Respondents of the Canadian Maternity Experiences Survey of 2006, all of whom were ≥ 15 years old	6,233 (weighted to n=74,523)	Higher odds of insufficient GWG (vs adequate) if immigrant; lower odds of excessive GWG if immigrant		Immigrant (yes/no)	No	S
Larouche, M.	2010	Canada	Retrospective	Medical record; Health Canada 2010 (IOM 2009)	Women who delivered at a health centre in Montreal from January 1998 - December 2007	960	Non-immigrants had higher GWG than women who immigrated to Canada >10 years before pregnancy (if restricted to women without hypertension, NS difference in GWG)	NS association between excessive GWG and recent immigration; NS difference in total GWG between non-immigrants and women who immigrated to Canada 10 years or less before pregnancy	Immigrant ≤ 5 yrs Immigrant >5-10 yrs Immigrant >10 yrs Non-immigrant	No	S & NS
Lowell, H.	2010	Canada	Retrospective	Self-reported; Health Canada 1999 IOM 1990)	Respondents of the 2006 national Maternity Experiences Survey, all of whom were ≥ 15 years old	5 554	Significantly higher prevalence of excessive GWG with Canadian-born women (vs foreign-born women); higher prevalence of insufficient GWG in foreign-born women		Country of birth: Canada or other	No	S
Pawlak, M.	2015	USA	Retrospective	Birth certificate; IOM 2009	Women who gave birth in Colorado from 2007-10	230 698	Increased odds of insufficient GWG in women living 0-9 years in USA (as compared to born in USA); decreased odds of excessive GWG if foreign-born (as compared to USA-born)	NS effect on odds of insufficient GWG if immigrated to USA 10+ years ago (as compared to USA-born)	Years lived in US: native born; ≥ 10 years; <10 years	No	S & NS
Reed, M. M.	2005	USA	Retrospective	Birth certificate; IOM 1985	Undocumented immigrants (primarily Mexican) receiving Emergency Medicaid and women from the general population who gave birth in Colorado from 1998-99	118 904	Insufficient GWG (< 20 lbs) significantly more prevalent in undocumented immigrants (compared to other women)		Undocumented immigrant; other women	No	S
Restall, A.	2014	New Zealand, Australia, Ireland	Prospective	Measured; IOM 2009	Multi-site cohort study with nulliparous women from 2004-11	1 950	Higher odds of excessive GWG if recent immigrant (within 5 years, as compared to not having immigrated within last 5 years)		Immigrant in past 5 years (yes/no)	No	S
Roville-Sausse, F.	2001	France	Retrospective	Medical record; no GWG guideline identified	Women who immigrated to France (from Turkey, Sub-Saharan Africa, North Africa, China, or Sri Lanka) and French nationals who attended prenatal care and gave birth at a specific hospital in Paris in 1997	559	When compared to non-immigrant French, all immigrant groups except Turkish experienced significantly lower GWG	NS difference in GWG between Turkish immigrants and non-immigrant French	France non-immigrant; immigrant from Maghreb; immigrant from Africa; immigrant from Turkey; immigrant from Sri Lanka; immigrant from China	No	S & NS
Sangi-Haghepykar, H.	2014	USA	Cross-sectional	Self-reported; IOM 2009	Hispanic women who delivered at a specific hospital in Texas	282	Higher odds of excessive GWG if USA born (vs non-US born)	Prevalence of insufficient vs adequate GWG not affected by being born in US vs elsewhere	US-born (yes/no)	Yes	S & NS
Siega-Riz, A. M.	1997	USA	Prospective	Measured; IOM 1990	Hispanic, primarily low-income women attending public prenatal clinics and who participated in a prematurity prevention project	6 114	Multivariate linear regression model for total GWG: positive association with being a US-born Hispanic	NS effect on odds of insufficient GWG (for all women): being a US-born Hispanic	US-born (yes/no)	Yes	S & NS

Tovar, A.	2012	USA	Prospective	Medical record; IOM 2009	Hispanic (Puerto Rican or Dominican Republic heritage) women who were either born in the Caribbean Island, had a parent born in the Caribbean Islands, or at least 2 grandparents born in the Caribbean Islands; all women gave birth at Baystate Medical Center from 2006-11	952	Higher odds of excessive GWG if US born (compared to Puerto Rico/Dominican Republic born), and higher total GWG if US born	NS effect of being born in US vs Puerto Rico/Dominican Republic on odds of insufficient GWG	Puerto-Rico/Dominican Republic born; US born	Yes	S & NS
Walker, L. O.	2014	USA	Retrospective	Birth certificate; IOM 2009	Hispanic and White non-Hispanic women who gave birth in 2009 in Texas and were ≥18 years old	250 857	Decreased odds of excessive GWG if not born in USA	NS effect of being US vs foreign born on odds of insufficient GWG	US-born (yes/no)	No	S & NS
Walker, L. O.	2009	USA	Retrospective	Self-reported; IOM 1990	Hispanic women who responded to the New Mexico Pregnancy Risk Assessment Monitoring System from 2000-03, all of whom were ≥18 years old	1 988	Significant differences in general GWG adequacy according to immigration status (US born vs not)	NS association between odds of insufficient GWG immigration status (US born vs not)	US-born (yes/no)	Yes	S & NS